

A review on arsenic pollution in West Bengal and Bihar : Cause, effects and remedial measures following latest technology

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Abstract : Arsenic contamination of ground water has been reported from many parts of West Bengal and Bihar since last few years. This review is compiled to summarize reasons and effects of contamination of arsenic in ground water and technologies currently being investigated to remove arsenic from ground water so that it can be acceptable for our use. The review comprises different theories and hypotheses that have been put forward from time to time for providing explanation for arsenic contamination. In some arsenic affected areas of West Bengal and Bihar, substitution of drinking water source by safe and easily available alternatives may not always be possible for implementation during part or whole of the year, or even if it is possible, may be very expensive. This paper will describe some safe water technologies for arsenic removal. Arsenic removal technologies are based on oxidation including solar oxidation, coagulation/co-precipitation, sedimentation, filtration, adsorption, ion exchange, membrane/reverse osmosis and biological process. The conventional technologies will be discussed to meet the requirements of households and communities which will be suitable for rural environment. Most commonly used arsenic removal units include fill and draw units, BCSIR Filter Unit, bucket treatment unit, activated alumina unit, use of iron coated sand, unit developed by Stevens Institute Technology and arsenic removal unit attached to tube-well. Some technologies utilize indigenous materials for arsenic removal. The paper will describe a short review of cause, effect of arsenic contamination and the technologies that may be used for arsenic removal in our country.

Keywords : Ground water, arsenic contamination, solar oxidation, coagulation, coprecipitation, filtration, adsorption, ion-exchange, reverse osmosis, biological process.

Introduction

The contamination of groundwater by arsenic in West Bengal and Bihar is one of the largest poisonings of a population in the history. The scale of this environmental poisoning disaster is greater than any seen before. In India, since the groundwater arsenic contamination was first surfaced from West Bengal in 1983, a number of other States, namely; Jharkhand, Bihar, Uttar Pradesh in flood plain of the Ganga river; Assam and Manipur in flood plain of the Brahmaputra and Imphal rivers, and Rajnandgaon village in Chhattisgarh state have chronically been exposed to drinking arsenic contaminated hand tube-wells water above permissible limit. In Bihar plains, ground water is the most important source of drinking and irrigation water. Many arsenic hotspots were detected in the four districts of Bihar (India), i.e. Patna, Bhojpur, Vaishali and Bhagalpur. The greatest frequency of contaminated hand pumps was noted in the eastern district of Bhagalpur¹.

Causes of arsenic pollution :

Historically arsenic is known as a poison. Arsenic (As) exists in several forms, which vary in toxicity and occurrence. The metallic form of arsenic (0 valency) is not absorbed by the stomach and intestines and does not exert adverse effects. On the other hand, a volatile compound such as AsH₃ is toxic, but is not present in water or food. Arsenite (+3) and arsenate (+5) are the most prevalent toxic forms of inorganic arsenic that are found in drinking water. As (+3) in reduced state in inorganic is a toxic pollutant in natural environment and is more soluble and mobile than the oxidized state of inorganic arsenic, arsenate As (+5).

The source of arsenic in groundwater can be traced out by establishing the relations between the river system (drainage pattern), the area from where the rivers brought sediments is parent materials. The problem of groundwater pollution by arsenic is found in inter fluvial region of

the Bhagirathi-Hugli and the Jalangi-Ichamati rivers lying mostly in the eastern part of the Bhagirathi-Hugli river of West Bengal. Source of arsenic in deltaic plain of West Bengal is considered to be the arsenic-rich sediments transported from the Chotonagpur Rajmahal Highlands^{2,3} and deposited in sluggish meandering streams under reducing conditions. Acharya *et al.*², has reported that the groundwater of Uttar Pradesh and Bihar has low concentrations of iron (0–700 µg/L) and, on this basis, commented that the relatively low value of dissolved iron upstream of the Ganges Delta indicates that the environment may not be sufficiently reducing to mobilize iron and arsenic. The source of the arsenic in groundwater is natural and arises because the water flows through arsenic-rich sediments.

The origin of the arsenic pollution is geological in this case – the arsenic is released to groundwater under naturally occurring aquifer conditions. Arsenic is one of the less abundant metalloids forming the earth's crust. Its important physicochemical characteristic is that it is commonly concentrated in sulphide-bearing mineral deposits, pyrites and hydrous iron oxides. Its presence in ground water sources is attributed to a number of natural and anthropogenic causes, based on its property of solubilizing in ground waters “depending on pH, redox conditions, and temperature and solution composition”⁴. Main sources of arsenic in aquifers include organic carbon or black shales, Holocene alluvial deposits, and volcanic sources. Of particular relevance to this study, is the “strongly reducing, arsenic-rich aquifers”⁵ of the young alluvial sediments of the Mid Ganga Plains. Arsenic occurs widely in aquifers of deltaic sediments and in deep sandy aquifer layers as fluvial deposits. It is introduced into the aquifer sediments in soluble state. The adsorption process and its consequent desorption are stated to be controlled by microbial activity within the concerned aquifers⁶. Additional processes promoting high arsenic content in ground water are oxidation and dissolution of arsenian pyrite, Fe[AsS]₂, and arsenopyrite [HN₈], FeAs⁷. Oxidation occurs either by infiltration of oxygenated ground waters⁸ or by lowering of ground water table into a stratigraphic zone of arsenic-rich sulphides⁹.

Oxidation of sulphide minerals (pyrite-FeS₂) was advocated strongly by many investigators in West Bengal as the cause of groundwater arsenic contamination¹⁰. Ac-

ording to this hypothesis, arsenic is released from the sulfide minerals (arseno-pyrite) in the shallow aquifer due to oxidation¹¹. The lowering of water table owing to over exploitation of groundwater for irrigation is the cause of release of arsenic. A recent research study explained that desorption or dissolution of arsenic from iron oxides could be the process on regional distributions of arsenic in water⁴. Broadly, it can be stated that some critical reactions to transform to reducing conditions and subsequent arsenic release are likely to take place to reduce arsenic from its oxidized (As^V) form to its reduced (As^{III}) form. Under many conditions, As^{III} is less strongly adsorbed to iron oxides than As^V. Dissolution of the iron oxides themselves under reducing conditions is another potentially important process. Some investigators explained that excessive use of water for irrigation and use of fertilizers have caused mobilization of phosphate from fertilizers down below the shallow aquifers, which have resulted in the mobilization of As due to anion exchange onto the reactive mineral surfaces. Sikdar and Chakraborty¹² attributed that the combined processes of recharge of groundwater from rainfall, sediment water interaction, groundwater flow, infiltration of irrigation return water (which is arsenic rich due to the use of arsenic-bearing pesticides, wood preservatives, etc. and the pumping of arsenic-rich groundwater for agriculture purpose), oxidation of natural or anthropogenic organic matter and the reductive dissolution of ferric iron and manganese oxides, played a key role in the evolution of groundwater arsenic contamination in the area. Recently, a new hypothesis based on displacement of arsenic by dissolved bicarbonate as an alternative mechanism for the genesis of high-arsenic groundwater has been proposed⁴.

Among few hypotheses proposed to explain the possible mechanism of arsenic groundwater contamination, most scientists have settled down to two hypotheses : (i) oxidation of arsenopyrite or arsenic rich pyrite in soil strata, and (ii) reductive dissolution of arsenic from soils. However, based on arsenic geochemistry, three hypotheses describing probable mechanisms of As mobilization in groundwater specially, with reference to Holocene aquifers like in West Bengal and Bangladesh, have been suggested¹³. These are :

(i) *Mobilization of arsenic due to the oxidation of As-bearing pyrite minerals* : Insoluble As bearing minerals,

such as arsenopyrite (FeAsS), are rapidly oxidized when exposed to atmosphere, realizing soluble As^{III}, sulfate (SO₄²⁻), and ferrous iron (Fe²⁺). The dissolution of these As-containing minerals is highly dependent on the availability of oxygen and the rate of oxidation of sulfide. The released As^{III} is partially oxidized to As^V by microbially mediated reactions. The chemical reaction is given by :

(ii) *Dissolution of As-rich iron oxyhydroxides (FeOOH) due to onset of reducing conditions in the subsurface* : Under oxidizing conditions, and in the presence of Fe, inorganic species of As are predominantly retained in the solid phase through interaction with FeOOH coatings on soil particles. The onset of reducing conditions in such environments can lead to the dissolution of FeOOH coatings. Fermentation of peat in the subsurface releases organic molecules (e.g. acetate) to drive reducing dissolution of FeOOH, resulting in release of Fe²⁺, As³⁺ and As⁵⁺ present on such coatings. The chemical reaction is given by :

where As_(s) is sorbed As, and As_(d) is dissolved As.

(iii) *Release of As sorbed to aquifer minerals by competitive exchange with phosphate (H₂PO₄⁻) ions that migrate into aquifers from the application of fertilizers to subsurface soil.*

The second mechanism involving dissolution of FeOOH under reducing conditions is considered to be the most probable reason for excessive accumulation of As in groundwater.

Effects of arsenic pollution :

Human health effects caused by exposure to arsenic (As) have been highlighted by recent regulatory initiatives in India. Arsenicosis is a chronic illness resulting from drinking water with high levels of As over a long period of time. It is commonly known as As poisoning. Humans may be exposed to arsenic through food, water and air. Exposure may also occur through skin contact with soil or water that contains arsenic. It is becoming clear that a drinking water quality guideline of 50 µg/L As is not protective. So, the World Health Organization¹⁴

has also reviewed As guidelines in drinking water and established a provisional guideline of 10 µg/L. Humans are exposed to organic and inorganic arsenic (As) from environmental and occupational sources. The main source of exposure (in terms of number of people affected) is environmental, naturally occurring inorganic As in drinking water¹⁵. The study by Rahman *et al.*¹⁶, in West Bengal, India, revealed that consumption of food from contaminated areas was another source of chronic As poisoning, since food products like vegetables and rice were cultivated using As-contaminated groundwater. Arsenic contamination of groundwater is one of the principal pathways of human exposure to inorganic¹⁷. Occurrence of As in groundwater of the Bengal Delta Plain in West Bengal is the largest emerging societal and environmental problem of the present century¹⁸⁻²⁰. Contaminated groundwater used to cultivate vegetables and rice consumed by people may be an important pathway of ingesting As^{21,22}.

Arsenic is a unique carcinogen²³. There is adequate evidence of carcinogenic risk by both inhalation and ingestion. Ferrecio *et al.*²⁴, presented a positive correlation between ingestion of inorganic As and lung cancer in humans in Chile. Hopenhayn-Rich *et al.*²⁵, showed that mortality from lung cancer was significantly increased with increasing As ingestion. According to Rossman *et al.*²⁶, arsenite can play a role in the enhancement of UV-induced skin cancers. Arsenite impairs nucleotide excision repair²⁷ and it may also affect gene expression by increasing or decreasing DNA methylation. Arsenic is associated with cancers of skin and internal organs, as well as with vascular disease (Luster and Simeonova²⁸). Chakraborti *et al.*²¹, showed higher As levels in hair, nail, and skin tissue of individuals with As-associated skin lesions. Darkening of skin (diffuse melanosis) in the whole body or on the palm of the hand is the earliest symptom. The high affinity of arsenic for sulfhydryl groups make keratin-rich cells (e.g. epidermal keratinocytes) a sensitive target for arsenic-induced toxicity. Arsenic has been shown to alter epidermal keratinocyte differentiation processes²⁹ induce overexpression of growth factors³⁰ and enhance proliferation of human keratinocytes. Diffuse or nodular keratosis on the palm of the hand and the sole of the foot is a sign of moderately severe toxicity. Rough dry skin, often with palpable nodules (spotted

keratosis), in dorsum of hands, feet, and legs are symptoms seen in severe cases. Squamous cell carcinoma; basal cell carcinoma; and carcinoma affecting the lung, uterus, bladder, genitourinary tract, or other sites are often seen in patients with advanced cases that have suffered for many years. Arsenical skin lesions in villagers of Semria Ojha Patti village in the Middle Ganga Plain, Bihar was also reported³¹.

Tsai *et al.*³², suggested that long term accumulated As may cause neurobehavioral effects in adolescence; therefore consumption of As in childhood may affect behavior later in life. Calderon *et al.*³³, reported that long-term memory, attention and the ability to understand speech may be affected by exposure to As in people with chronic malnutrition. Study by Wasserman *et al.*³⁴, reported that children more than 50 µg/L As exposure had lower performance scores than children with less than 5.5 µg/L exposure. Pregnancy complications were found due to chronic exposure of As from groundwater. In women increased fetal loss and premature delivery were found with increased As exposure³¹. Hopenhayn *et al.*³⁵, found that women exposed to As in drinking water during pregnancy have changes in urinary excretion and metabolite distribution that can cause toxic effects on the developing fetus. Milton *et al.*³⁶, indicated a strong link between chronic As exposure and spontaneous abortion and stillbirth. Long term exposure to As is an independent risk factor for atherosclerosis³⁷.

Guha Mazumder *et al.*³⁸, reported that long-term ingestion of inorganic arsenic can cause respiratory effects and evidences of obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), interstitial lung disease (ILD). Bronchiectasis were found in some of the cases³⁹. Results of studies carried out by Guha Mazumder³⁹, on people showing features of Arsenicosis due to drinking arsenic contaminated water provided evidence that arsenic was a potent respiratory toxicant. Respiratory effects in West Bengal were first noted in 1995 when 57% of the 156 patients who lived in arsenic-affected villages reported having cough⁴⁰. Patients with chronic As exposure have skin manifestations associated with weakness, conjunctival congestion, redness of the eyes, chronic cough, and chronic bronchitis (inflammation of the respiratory tract)⁴¹.

Different doses of As can affect hormone regulation in cells at different levels. In animals and cell cultures, arsenic can disrupt hormonal (endocrine) processes as

well as gene expression, at low doses similar to those found in the environment⁴². Inorganic As is diabetogenic in humans, but little is known about pathophysiological mechanisms^{43,44}.

So, chronic exposure to As is associated with pigmentation, keratosis, skin cancer, weakness, anemia, dyspepsia, enlargement of the liver, spleen, and ascites (fluid in abdomen)⁴⁵. Mukherjee *et al.*⁴⁶, found that the longer the time of exposure, the more severe the signs and symptoms of As toxicity. In a study in West Bengal, Rahman *et al.*¹⁶, showed that patient with As-related skin lesions were using water with As levels of 800 µg/L, as a result, many patients with skin lesions also suffered from cancer.

Fig. 1. Arsenic lesions on feet, extreme. Fig. 2. Keratosis Sole. Fig. 3. Spotted keratosis on palm.

Remedial measures following latest technology :

Numerous arsenic removal technologies have been developed. These technologies can be classified into different categories based on the dominant removal process. These processes are : (1) Oxidation, (2) Coagulation/Co-Precipitation, (3) Sedimentation, (4) Filtration, (5) Adsorption, (6) Ion Exchange, (7) Membrane/Reverse Osmosis, (8) Biological and (9) Other.

Oxidation : Of the two predominant forms of arsenic in water, arsenate (As^V) and arsenite (As^{III}), most treatment processes are effective at removing arsenate, but not arsenite. Arsenite is typically non-charged below pH 9.2. Treatment often includes an oxidation step to convert arsenite to arsenate. Aeration, the supplying of air, oxidizes arsenic, converting arsenite to arsenate, and the iron that co-occurs. This is precipitated as $FeAsO_4$. Arsenic can also be oxidized by a number of other chemicals including chlorine, hypochlorite, ozone, permangan-

ate, hydrogen peroxide and Fenton's reagent ($\text{H}_2\text{O}_2/\text{Fe}^{2+}$). Photochemical oxidization proceeds from the reaction of radiant energy and a chemical system.

Passive sedimentation : Passive sedimentation received considerable attention because of rural people's habit of drinking stored water from pitchers. Oxidation of water during collection and subsequent storage in houses may cause a reduction in arsenic concentration in stored water (*Bashi Pani*). Experiments conducted showed zero to high reduction in arsenic content by passive sedimentation. Arsenic reduction by plain sedimentation appears to be dependent on water quality particularly the presence of precipitating iron in water. Ahmed *et al.*⁴⁷, showed that more than 50% reduction in arsenic content is possible by sedimentation of tube-well water containing 380–480 mg/L of alkalinity as CaCO_3 and 8–12 mg/L of iron but cannot be relied to reduce arsenic to desired level.

Solar oxidation : Solar oxidation and removal of arsenic (SORAS) is a simple method of solar oxidation of arsenic in transparent bottles to reduce arsenic content of drinking water. Ultraviolet radiation can catalyze the process of oxidation of arsenite in presence of other oxidants like oxygen. The SORAS method is based on photochemical oxidation of As^{III} followed by precipitation or filtration of As^{V} adsorbed on Fe^{III} oxides as shown in Fig. 4. This process on average can reduce arsenic content of water to about one-third. It could be a water treatment method used at household level to treat small quantities of drinking water.

Fig. 4. Basic principle of SORAS with illumination, photochemical formation of the reactive oxidants for the oxidation of As^{III} to As^{V} and precipitation of iron(III)(hydr)oxides with adsorbed As^{V} .

Coagulation/filtration : Coagulation/filtration removes arsenic by coprecipitation and adsorption using iron coagulants. Coagulation/filtration using alum is already used by some utilities to remove suspended solids and may be adjusted to remove arsenic. Mechanisms and results in the overall process includes of particle growth (floc formation) and particle aggregation within a water being treated, including *in situ* coagulant formation, chemical particle destabilization and physical inter-particle contacts. Coagulation converts soluble arsenic into insoluble reaction products, allowing separation by sedimentation and/or filtration. Factors affecting arsenic removal by coagulation/precipitation include coagulant type and dose, mixing time and speed, pH, arsenic oxidation state and concentration, presence of inorganic solutes. Water treatment with coagulants such as aluminium alum, $\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$, ferric chloride FeCl_3 and ferric sulfate $\text{Fe}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ are effective in removing arsenic from water. Ferric salts have been found to be more effective in removing arsenic.

Alum dissolution :

Aluminium precipitation (acidic) :

Co-precipitation (non-stoichiometric, non-defined product) :

$\text{Al-As (complex)} + \text{other products}$

Three mechanisms are potentially involved in arsenic removal : (i) precipitation : the formation of insoluble compounds $\text{Al}(\text{AsO}_4)$ or $\text{Fe}(\text{AsO}_4)$, (ii) co-precipitation : incorporation of soluble arsenic species into the metal hydroxide floc, (iii) adsorption : the electrostatic binding of soluble arsenic to the external surfaces of the insoluble metal hydroxides.

Iron oxide adsorption filters the water through a granular medium containing ferric oxide. Ferric oxide has a high affinity for adsorbing dissolved metals such as arsenic. The iron oxide medium eventually becomes saturated, and must be replaced. Similar reactions take place in case of ferric chloride and ferric sulfate with the formation of Fe-As complex as end product which is removed by the process of sedimentation and filtration. The

possible reactions of arsenate with hydrous iron oxide are shown below where $[\text{FeOH}^{\circ}]$ represents oxide surface site^{48,49}.

Richmond *et al.*⁵⁰, indicated that the overall efficiency of arsenic removal involves a combination of both supersaturation and pH effects, with pH controlling the affinity of arsenate for the ferrihydrite surface, and supersaturation controlling the surface area and physical properties of the ferrihydrite product.

Activated alumina is another filter medium known to effectively remove dissolved arsenic. It has also been used to remove undesirably high concentrations of fluoride. Arsenic adsorbed on aluminium hydroxide flocs as Al-As complex is removed by sedimentation. Filtration may be required to ensure complete removal of all flocs. Activated alumina, Al_2O_3 , having good sorptive surface is an effective medium for arsenic removal. When water passes through a packed column of activated alumina, the impurities including arsenic present in water are adsorbed on the surfaces of activated alumina grains. Eventually the column becomes saturated, first at its upstream zone and later the saturated zone moves downstream towards the bottom end and finally the column get totally saturated. Regeneration of saturated alumina is carried out by exposing the medium to 4% caustic soda, NaOH, either in batch or by flow through the column resulting in a high arsenic contaminated caustic waste water. The residual caustic soda is then washed out and the medium is neutralized with a 2% solution of sulfuric acid rinse. During the process about 5–10% alumina is lost and the capacity of the regenerated medium is reduced by 30–40%. The activated alumina needs replacement after 3–4 regeneration.

Ion exchange has long been used as a water-softening process, although usually on a single-home basis. It can also be effective in removing arsenic with a net ionic charge. It is noted that arsenic oxide, As_2O_3 , is a common form of arsenic in groundwater that is soluble, but has no net charge. Synthetic ion exchange resins are based on a cross-linked polymer matrix, typically composed of polystyrene cross-linked with vinyl benzene. Charged func-

tional groups are attached to the matrix through covalent bonding and fall into four groups⁵¹: strongly acidic, weakly acidic, strongly basic, weakly basic. Various strong base anion exchange resins are commercially available that can effectively remove arsenate from water, producing effluents with less than 1 ug/L arsenic.

Conventional sulfate-selective resins are particularly suited for arsenate removal. Nitrate-selective resins also remove arsenic. Ion exchangers are typically down-flow, packed bed columns with ion exchange resin beads pre-saturated with an exchangeable ion. Source water is passed through the packed bed until the appearance of the unwanted contaminant in the effluent. At this stage, the ion exchange media is reactivated with a regenerant solution and rinsed with water in preparation for another treatment cycle. Both the redox potential and pH are important factors with regard to arsenic removal by ion exchange.

Membrane/reverse osmosis: Membrane separation uses semi-permeable membranes that are selectively permeable to water and certain solutes to separate impurities from water. Membranes are able to remove many different kinds of dissolved solids, including arsenic, from water. However, they are usually expensive and therefore are typically considered in applications such as desalination, brackish water conversion and for removal of specific ions, such as arsenic, that are difficult to remove by other means. There are many different membrane alternatives including microfiltration, reverse osmosis, electrodialysis, ultrafiltration and nanofiltration.

Biological: Biological treatment transforms, stabilizes and/or removes arsenic by means of microorganisms. Microorganisms, primarily certain specific bacteria, accomplish this by oxidation/reduction, mineralization, detoxification or methylation. Jahan *et al.*⁵², used a common green algae *Scenedesmus abundans* for determining arsenic uptake. Algae morphology studies indicated that the algae cells were impacted due to the presence of arsenic as evidenced by clumping or loss of cell clusters. However algae and sludge disposal would pose a problem and will have to be dealt with accordingly. Pokhrel *et al.*⁵³, reported that biological activated carbon (BAC) filter, system was highly effective in the removal of both arsenic and iron. On average, it removed 97% of arsenic

and 99.8% of iron.

Other : Other methods in providing arsenic-free drinking include : dugwell, deeper tube-well, pond, rainwater harvesting.

The most commonly used arsenic removal units are may be used for arsenic removal in our country discussed below.

Fill and draw units : It is a community type treatment unit. It is 600 L capacity (effective) tank with slightly tapered bottom for collection and withdrawal of settled sludge. The tank is fitted with a manually operated mixer with flat-blade impellers. The tank is filled with arsenic contaminated water and required quantity of oxidant and coagulant are added to the water. The water is then mixed for 30 s by rotating the mixing device at the rate of 60 rpm and left overnight for sedimentation. The water takes some times to become completely still which helps flocculation. The floc formation is caused by the hydraulic gradient of the rotating water in the tank. The settled water is then drawn through a pipe fitted at a level, few inches above the bottom of the tank and passed through a sand bed and finally collected through a tap for drinking purpose as shown in Fig. 5. The mixing and flocculation processes in this unit are better controlled to effect higher removal of arsenic.

Fig. 5. Fill and draw arsenic removal unit.

BCSIR filter unit : Bangladesh Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (BCSIR) has developed an arsenic removal system, which uses the process of coagulation/coprecipitation with an iron based chemical followed by sand filtration.

Bucket treatment unit : The Bucket Treatment Unit (BTU), is based on the principles of coagulation, co-precipitation and adsorption processes. It consists of two buckets each 20 liter capacity, placed one above the other. Chemicals are mixed manually with arsenic contaminated

water in the upper red bucket by vigorous stirring with a wooden stick for 30 to 60 s and then flocculated by gentle stirring for about 90 s. The mixed water is then allowed to settle for 1–2 h. The water from the top red bucket is then allowed to flow into the lower green bucket via plastic pipe and a sand filter installed in the lower bucket. The flow is initiated by opening a valve fitted slightly above the bottom of the red bucket to avoid inflow of settled sludge in the upper bucket. The lower green bucket is practically a treated water container. These units are based on chemical doses of 200 mg/L aluminum sulfate and 2 mg/L of potassium permanganate supplied in crushed powder form. The units were reported to have very good performance in arsenic removal in both field and laboratory conditions^{54,55}. Poor mixing and variable water quality particularly pH of groundwater may appeared to be the cause of poor performance in rapid assessment.

Fig. 6. Bucket treatment unit.

Sorptive filtration media : Several sorptive media have been reported to remove arsenic from water. These are activated alumina, activated carbon, iron and manganese coated sand, kaolinite clay, hydrated ferric oxide, activated bauxite, titanium oxide, silicium oxide and many natural and synthetic media. The efficiency of all some sorptive media depend on the use of oxidizing agent as aids to sorption of arsenic.

Activated alumina unit : Activated alumina, Al_2O_3 , having good sorptive surface is an effective medium for arsenic removal. Some of the activated alumina based sorptive media used include : BUET Activated Alumina, Alcan Enhanced Activated Alumina.

The BUET and Alcan activated alumina have been extensively tested in field condition in different areas of Bangladesh under rapid assessment and found very effec-

Fig. 7. Alcan enhanced activated alumina.

tive in arsenic removal. The Arsenic Removal Units (ARUs) of Project Earth Industries Inc. (USA) used hybrid aluminas and composite metal oxides as adsorption media and were able to treat 200–500 Bed Volume (BV) of water containing 550 g/L of arsenic and 14 mg/L of iron. The Apyron Technologies Inc. (ATI) also uses inorganic granular metal oxide based media that can selectively remove As^{III} and As^V from water. The Aqua-Bind™ arsenic media used by ATI consist of non-hazardous aluminium oxide and manganese oxide for cost-effective removal of arsenic. The proponents claimed that the units installed in India and Bangladesh consistently reduced arsenic to less than 10 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (BAMWSP, DFID and WaterAid Bangladesh⁵⁶).

Iron coated sand : Iron coated sand has been prepared following a procedure similar to that adopted by Joshi and Choudhury⁵⁷. The iron content of the iron coated sand was found to be 25 mg/g of sand. Raw water having 300 $\mu\text{g/L}$ of arsenic when filtered through iron coated sand becomes essentially arsenic-free. It was found that 350 bed volumes could be treated satisfying the drinking water standard of 50 ppb. The saturated medium is regenerated by passing 0.2 N sodium hydroxide through the column or soaking the sand in 0.2 N sodium hydroxide followed by washing with distilled water. No significant change in bed volume (BV) in arsenic removal was found after 5 regeneration cycles. It is noted that iron coated sand is equally effective in removing both As^{III} and As^V . Iron coated brick dust has also been developed in Bangladesh for arsenic removal from drinking water.

MRT-1000 and Reid System Ltd. : This system shows a arsenic(III) removal efficiency more than 80%. This system could effectively reduce arsenic content along with other impurities in water. The capital and operational costs of the reverse osmosis system would be relatively high.

Stevens Institute Technology : This technology also uses two buckets, one to mix chemicals (reported to be

iron sulphate and calcium hypochloride) supplied in packets and the other to separate flocs by the processes of sedimentation and filtration. The second bucket has a second inner bucket with slits on the sides as shown in Fig. 8 to help sedimentation and keeping the filter sand bed in place. The chemicals form visible large flocs on mixing by stirring with stick. Rapid assessment showed that the technology was effective in reducing arsenic levels to less than 0.05 mg/L in case of 80 to 95% of the samples tested (Ahmed and Rahaman⁵⁸). The sand bed used for filtration is quickly clogged by flocs and requires washing atleast twice a week.

Fig. 8. Stevens Institute Technology.

Arsenic removal unit attached to tube-well : The principles of arsenic removal by alum coagulation, sedimentation and filtration have been employed in a compact unit for water treatment in the village level in West Bengal, India. The arsenic removal plant attached to hand tube-well as shown in Fig. 9 has been found effective in removing 90% arsenic from tube-well water having initial arsenic concentration of 300 mg/L. The treatment process involves addition of sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl), and aluminum alum in diluted form, mixing, flocculation, sedimentation and up flow filtration in a compact unit.

Fig. 9. Arsenic removal plants attached to tube-well (designed and constructed in India).

Conclusion :

Arsenic mitigation included both household and community options which efficiently removes arsenic. This

paper describes cause, effect of arsenic contamination and the technologies that may be safe and easily used for arsenic removal in our country.

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